

**RE.
CAP**

Reinforcing CAP

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Glossary

API	Application programming interface
BBOX	Bounding Box
BPS	Basic Payment Scheme
CAP	Common Agricultural Policy
CC	Cross Compliance
DRF	Diango REST Framework
LPIS	Land Parcel Identification System
NDVI	Normalised Difference Vegetation Index
PA	Paying agency
RGB	Red Green Blue colour model
RS	Remote Sensing
SDK	Software development kit
WMS	Web Map service

Executive Summary

This document aims to outline the steps that were followed and the decision that were made in order to develop and deliver the first version of the RECAP web and mobile application. Furthermore, it documents the integration practices, functional and non-functional requirements and the development of a testing methodology in order to present the first release of the RECAP platform which illustrates a solid and functional version. Further development and improvements will continuously be implemented over the next period so as to deliver a valuable tool for all users.

Specifically, this deliverable aims at describing the progress made in WP3 during the duration of the work package. Moreover, it presents the 1st version of RECAP platform and its components; outlines the progress made by the development team since the previous deliverable; describes any changes that might have occurred in the architecture during the development period; and describes the integration between the components and the core platform. Finally, the document depicts the next steps that are planned for right after the delivery of the platform.

The web platform can be found at: <http://app.recap-h2020.eu>

Specifically, the deliverable covers the following topics:

- **Chapter 1:** Progress towards RECAP platform
- **Chapter 2:** RECAP architecture
- **Chapter 3:** App functionality
- **Chapter 4:** Conclusions

1 Progress towards RECAP platform

The RECAP platform aims to facilitate the Common Agricultural Policy (CAP) workflow between farmers, inspectors and paying agencies (PA) and assist through the use of remote sensing data to extract meaningful information. It was evident from D2.2 (Report of user requirements in relation to the RECAP platform) that the RECAP platform was comprised of five different workflows (one for each pilot), due to the differences between the pilots and the rules interpretation. Due to that, the RECAP platform was developed as an integrated system, composed of core functionalities which are commonly shared to the pilots, and additionally pilot specific functionalities were built on top of that.

1.1 Development methodology

The Scrum¹ methodology was used for the development of the platform. All user stories from D2.2 (Report of user requirements in relation to the RECAP platform) were collected and placed on an online tool (PivotalTracker² and Trello³) to assist the easy monitoring of the development tasks (Figure 1). As the application mainly contains lengthy processes tied to a large workflow, it didn't make sense to have retrospective meetings with stakeholders based on the outcome of small sprints, therefore the team produced larger parts of the application which were then demonstrated to the users during the co-creation meetings and feedback was collected. That feedback was processed in documents and then put to the online tool where tasks were further broken down for the developers to work on.

Figure 1: PivotalTracker for the specifications and managing of the development

Taiga⁴ was used as an issue tracking system, where testers and RECAP partners were reporting issues tracked during their use of the application (Figure 2).

¹ [https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Scrum_\(software_development\)](https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Scrum_(software_development))

² <https://www.pivotaltracker.com>

³ <https://www.trello.com>

⁴ <https://tree.taiga.io>

Type	Severity	Priority	Votes	Subject	Status	Created
●	●	●	▲ 0	#57 lithuania_maps	New	22 Aug 2017
●	●	●	▲ 0	#56 lithuania_Maps	New	21 Aug 2017
●	●	●	▲ 0	#55 Lithuania_Farm.Profile.Add.Geometry	New	11 Aug 2017
●	●	●	▲ 0	#54 lithuania_farm_profile	New	09 Aug 2017
●	●	●	▲ 0	#53 lithuania_My.Documents	Ready for test	03 Aug 2017
●	●	●	▲ 0	#52 lithuania_FarmProfile_validations	New	03 Aug 2017
●	●	●	▲ 0	#51 Login not working	Ready for test	17 Jul 2017
●	●	●	▲ 0	#50 Step 3	Ready for test	14 Jul 2017
●	●	●	▲ 0	#49 Serbia_Step 2	Ready for test	14 Jul 2017
●	●	●	▲ 0	#48 Serbia - Step 1	Closed	14 Jul 2017
●	●	●	▲ 0	#47 Serbia_Step 1_Undo	New	14 Jul 2017
●	●	●	▲ 0	#46 Serbia - Step 1 - "add geometry"	New	14 Jul 2017
●	●	●	▲ 0	#45 Setting Reminders is a it too complicated	Ready for test	12 Jul 2017
●	●	●	▲ 0	#44 spain_work.diary_I.E.	New	12 Jul 2017
●	●	●	▲ 0	#43 chain reminders: delete button	Closed	12 Jul 2017

Figure 2: Taiga used as the issue tracking system

1.2 Co-Production meetings

During March and June, the WP3 team participated in the organisation of the co-production meetings. A sub-group of stakeholders have been gathered for consultation at strategic points in development of RECAP platform. The aim of these meetings is to ensure customisation of the platform to make it suitable for each pilot country (with regards to language, cultural needs and data requirements); to gather valuable feedback from the perspective of the different user groups; to identify a range of minor issues; to establish some important considerations for the operability of the RECAP platform that have resulted in technical advancements in WP3.

1.3 User Experience

The RECAP application tries to engage three different type of users (farmers, inspectors and PA) so it should fit their needs. It should be easy to use, well organized and attractive, but in the same time functional and able to store and serve the different types of data. After going through the user requirements from D2.2 (Report of user requirements in relation to the RECAP platform), the development team drafted wireframes for the farmer part of the application (Figure 3).

Figure 3: RECAP Wireframes

The wireframes were discussed among the consortium and during a co-creation workshop with farmers and the result were handed to designers, who took up the creation of the user interface (Figure 4). Similar strategies were followed for the development of the inspector and PA mockups of the platform.

Figure 4: RECAP mockup proposal by the designers

The development team was based on those initial mockups to build all other RECAP screens and was engaging the designers on demand to assist improving or solving complex user experience problems. Further improvements on the user interface are expected to be requested during the pilot phase.

1.4 Integration

1.4.1 Integration among the RECAP components

The integration plan was described in D3.1 (RECAP System Architecture) and covered the connection among the RECAP components to work under one common roof. Furthermore, D3.3 (Software components development) touched the development of the components and the integration plan between those and the web application (front end) was described.

1.4.2 Integration among the Remote Sensing (RS) component

The biggest challenge was the integration with the Remote Sensing (RS) component due to the fact that it is hosted at NOA premises and it needed to trigger a lengthy process which involves the download and parsing of large satellite data chunks.

It was decided that the PAs will trigger a process on the RS servers and, when the results are ready, they will be passed to the RECAP API in order to be ingested in the database:

1. The registered and authorized user draws an Area Of Interest (AOI) in the map component of the RECAP platform.
2. The polygon, along with the farmers' declaration within the AOI are extracted from the RECAP database and passed to the Remote Sensing component through a POST call.
3. This POST action triggers the automatic remote sensing workflows relevant to cross-compliance and greening rules.
4. When the workflows are finished, the values of a set of alphanumeric variables are updated in the RS component internal database. Each parcel in the AOI is associated with this set of variables. The variables are shown in Table 1 have been agreed between NOA and DRAXIS.

Table 1: Remote Sensing variables used for cross-compliance and greening checks

Cross-compliance checks with RS and attributes per parcel		
Attribute code	Attribute description	Attribute type
Green1	Diversification of crops	Boolean (checked or not checked)
Green2	Maintenance of permanent grassland	Boolean (checked or not checked)
GAEC4	Minimum Soil Cover	Boolean (checked or not checked)
NDVI	Normalised Difference Vegetation Index	Float
PSRI	Plant senescence reflectance index	Float
SAVI	Soil-adjusted vegetative index	Float
SeasType	Seasonal Label Estimation	String (summer, winter, permanent)

FarmType	Crop Family Label Estimation	String
CropType	Lowest level of crop specificity	Integer (from lookup table)
GAEC6	Crop residue burning residues	Boolean (checked or not checked)
BurnPerc	Percentage of the parcel that is burnt	Float
BurnTimestamp	Month of the year for which the burned area was mapped	Integer
SMR1	Water pollution risk assessment – Risk Indicator	Boolean (checked or not checked)
GAEC1	Comply with buffer zones	Boolean (checked or not checked)
GAEC5	Soil Erosion/ Poor tillage	Boolean (checked or not checked)
Slope	Average parcel slope angle	Float (decimal degrees)
Aspect	Average parcel aspect angle	Float (decimal degrees)
K-factor	Soil erosivity depended on the ground composition (clay, sandy, etc.)	Float
C-factor	Soil erosivity according to land/cover and tillage practices	Float
SoilErIndx	Product of K-factor and C-factor	Float
RUSLE	Revised Universal Soil Loss Equation	Float
WaterProx	Distance between parcel and closet watercourse	Float
Risk Index	Parcel risk assessment for water pollution	String (V. Low, Low, Medium, High, V. High)

- The values attributed to the different variables update then the corresponding parcels table in the RECAP database (via an API call), for further exploitation and decision making.
- Finally, the satellite imagery that was used to generated the RS information, is being made available to RECAP users through a Mapserver WMS service available from NOA's RS server.

1.5 Development of components

The development of the components was covered extensively in D3.3 (Software components development). The components developed were: a) workflow, b) spatial, c) extractor, d) remote sensing and e) the SDK.

1.6 Testing

During the testing procedure, the team developed the essential mechanisms to test and validate the platform's behaviour compared to the initial "vision" and the WP2 "user stories" for the RECAP platform established at the first stage of the development and reassure that the platform will function securely and reliably. The testing procedure helped the team track and resolve issues both in code but also in the logic of

the events. Several scenarios were written in paper and some of them were also automated using tools like Selenium⁵ so the tests were executed right before a version gets published. Other scenarios were analyzed in steps and were given to pilot users to execute and track any issues or inconsistencies.

A list of scenarios and their steps can be found in Annex I – RECAP Testing Scenarios.

⁵ <http://www.seleniumhq.org/>

2 RECAP Architecture

2.1 Revised Architecture (decisions, problems)

The RECAP architecture as it was presented in D3.1 (RECAP System Architecture) was followed without significant changes. There were minor additions and update introduced and are documented below. The final architecture diagram is presented in Figure 5.

Figure 5: RECAP architecture

The most significant updates and decisions for the architecture compared to the one in D3.1 (RECAP System Architecture) and D3.3 (Software components development) are listed here:

API endpoints

The RECAP platform is based on a RESTful API and all data are served through it. The API was developed based on Django REST Framework (DRF) with its additional packages. The biggest challenge faced, was to be able to serve both, current or history data to the different pilots and user roles. The solution was to have one main API endpoint for the common functionalities (e.g. /bps) and five different endpoints, one for each pilot, for the functionalities that are pilot specific (e.g. /bps_gr). Pilot specific API endpoint groups are developed on top of the main groups. Figure 6 presents the most important groups of the API endpoints.

Figure 6: RECAP Restful API

User ID and BPS ID are added to the API endpoints where is needed (e.g. /user/{user_id}/{bps_id}) in order to retrieve the data for the specific user and his/her BPS. Following this example users (farmer, inspector, PA) can access their historic data, or other users' data through the API, by updating the combination of user id and bps id. All calls are taken searched to verify that the user has access to see something before that gets returned to him/her.

All the API endpoints were documented using Swagger⁶ and the documentation (Figure 7) can be found here:

https://app.swaggerhub.com/apis/sekulcaleksandar/swagger-api_RECAP/1

Figure 7: RECAP API swagger documentation

Notifications and reminders

Celery⁷, an asynchronous task queue was added to the architecture in order to queue and send notifications and reminders to the users asynchronously. Initially the API was handling this job internally with cron jobs, but as it proved the things to monitor were gradually increasing giving extra burden to DJANGO. Now the celery worker is responsible to maintain a queue and it remains active, monitoring every five seconds for changes in the RECAP main entities (e.g. BPS activities, LPIS, etc.).

Serving static layers

The initial approach was to use Geoserver⁸ to serve static vector and raster data (etc. map layers, natura2000, land use, slope). The pilots' requested only vector data to show up on a map, so currently there is no raster data repository feeding Geoserver. Vector data are stored in a PostGIS⁹ database which can efficiently render map segments and allows the possibility to perform spatial queries using parcel geometries. Each pilot has its own Geoserver workspace, in order to facilitate the presentation of their specific static layers over the map.

Another change from the original plan concerns the storage of the remote sensing results. Initially the plan was for the results to be stored in the PostGIS database and be served through Geoserver. A better

⁶ <http://swagger.io/>

⁷ <http://www.celeryproject.org/>

⁸ <http://geoserver.org/>

⁹ <http://postgis.net/>

approach that assists a potential scaling of the application was to host the results on the remote sensing server where all the work takes place. That reduced significantly the need to transfer data from one part of the application to another.

Remote Sensing component architecture

The RS component was developed to work independently of the RECAP platform if fed with the proper data. A high-level view of the RS component architecture component is shown in Figure 8. There were no significant changes implemented with respect to the foreseen architecture in D3.1 (RECAP System Architecture).

Figure 8: RS components architecture diagram

Data flow scenario between the remote sensing component and the RECAP platform

Integration and data workflow between RECAP platform and Remote Sensing component is slightly changed than the one described in the previous deliverables. To demonstrate the offered functionality a sequence of actions is presented:

- 1) A PA user draws BBOX on the map which sends a GeoJSON to the RS server (hosted by NOA)
- 2) At the RS server this triggers a process chain to extract the essential information from satellite images
- 3) Upon completion of the process, the results of the Remote Sensing component are sent back to the RECAP API which updates the specific attributes of the Parcel model in the database
- 4) The PA user gets notified of the results availability and he gets in the platform
 - a. the Spatial component (i.e. map) sends a WMS request to ask for the RGB images and NDVI indices of the Sentinel 2 images from the RS server (NOA premises)
 - b. RS server responds
 - c. Spatial component presents that data to the user

Frontend technology change

In the initial RECAP architecture, the React¹⁰ JavaScript framework was chosen as the technology for developing the web and mobile frontend. The development team decided to use AngularJS¹¹ instead, because of the more available experience within the team, but also the fact that React demanded to re-implement pieces of code for specific target platforms which is not the case with Angular.

Technologies used

The list of the technologies used in the RECAP architecture are presented below:

Table 2: The technologies used in RECAP

Modules	Technology used
Rest API	Django REST Framework
Database storage	Postgress/PostGIS
File Storage	A common file storage based on linux
Notifications	Celery
GIS server	MapServer
Web Server	Apache
Web App	AngularJS
Web Map App	OpenLayers3, Geodjango
Mobile App	Cordova to build natively for Android, iOS

¹⁰ <https://facebook.github.io/react/>

¹¹ <https://angularjs.org/>

2.2 Revised User Stories

Most of the user stories have already been implemented. The ones still left in the backlog are related to the mobile application or are issues still not resolved or contain new functionality that was received later in the project from co-creation meetings. An indicative list of user stories that were created during the course of the project:

- User should be able to print the map
- During farm creation user needs to be asked generic questions (e.g. do you have livestock and if yes, we need to hide related questions).
- User needs to have a tool for drawing and measuring length and perform a spatial query on the Map
- User should be able to create reminders for activities
- User should have access to his/her work diary
- User should be able to filter items from the log history
- PA admin user should be able to confirm who is an inspector or PA user
- During registration, user should be able to choose their preferred user role: farmer, inspector or PA
- Inspector should be able to filter farmers list by BPS ID
- Farmer user should be able to upload documents that will be available to the inspectors at all times.
- User should be able to download all of the documents at once

3 App functionality

This chapter details the first version of the RECAP platform that will be used by the pilot users to test and validate some of the main services and functionalities. This first release of the platform is as complete as needed for the pilot operation. The users of the five pilot cases will provide an evaluation of their satisfaction with the current RECAP solution in order to determine to which extent the RECAP solution meets the requirements initially defined and what additional features and characteristics should be added.

There are three different user roles within the RECAP system:

- The farmer role
- The inspector role
- The paying agency role

D3.3 (Software components development) described the various components of the RECAP platform and detailed how these were implemented as well as how they communicate with each other.

Two mobile applications are currently under development; a smartphone optimized application dedicated to the farmers' needs and another one focusing on the inspectors' needs. The mobile application is mainly for the data collection on the farmer's field either from the farmer or from the inspector for on-the-spot checks. Consequently, the mobile app is a secondary user environment as the main one is the web application.

3.1 Web application

3.1.1 Farmers

After completing the registration, the users land on the dashboard in which they have to fill in the fields with all the needed farm-related data. This required data is the same data needed for the completion of the Basic Payment Scheme (BPS) application. Based on the user's input, the system decides which Cross Compliance (CC) rules apply to their fields. Figure 9 depicts the BPS form. In order to be more user-friendly and help user to keep up with no extremely long lists, the BPS form is split in steps.

Edit BPS data

Name of the physical person or legal form and name of legal entity:
e.g. Anvydas or Farm Inc.

Personal code of the physical person or code of legal person:
Max 11 characters allowed

Street name, house no., flat no., according to the place of residence
e.g. Utenos g. 99-101

Legal form and name of legal entity:
e.g. Farm Inc.

Municipality according to the place of residence:
e.g. Kaunas

Surname of the physical person:
e.g. Sabonis

Parish according to the place of residence:
Enter parish name

Village according to the place of residence
e.g. Konceptas

Phone number:
Enter contact phone number

E-mail address:
e.g. johndoe@example.com

Holding No.:
Enter holding number

Account Number: _____ Year of Application: _____

Figure 9: Filling in the farm profile

On the final step the user is able to associate each previously-declared parcel with specific CC rules. This helps the user who owns more than one parcels not to enter multiple times the same information.

Description	Mark box if true	Relevant parcels
Do you have at least 0.01ha of the farm in the water protection zone?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="button" value="parcels"/>
Do you have at least 0.01ha of the farm in the areas sensitive for erosion?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="button" value="parcels"/>
Do you have have state kept botanical heritage objects in your declared area or have at least 0.01 ha of the farm in Natura 2000 sites?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="button" value="parcels"/>
Do you have at least one type of these animals: horses, sheep, cattle, goats, ducks, mink, bison, fallow deer, turkeys, pigs, martens, foxes, mouffons, ostrich, bison, chinchilla, rabbits, chickens, geese?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="button" value="parcels"/>
Is at least 0.01 ha of the farm in Natura 2000 sites?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="button" value="parcels"/>
Are you a food (milk, honey, eggs) producer?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="button" value="parcels"/>
Do you have cattle?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="button" value="parcels"/>
Do you have pigs?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="button" value="parcels"/>
Do you have sheep and/or goat?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="button" value="parcels"/>
Do you have (or will have in the future) calves?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="button" value="parcels"/>
Do you have at least one animal (except pigeons, snails, earthworms, roe deers, bisons, wild boars, wolves, lynxes, bears, owls, swan, coon, parrots, skunk, elks, hares, hawk, zebras, capercaille, camels, other pets, pumas)?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="button" value="parcels"/>

Figure 10: Correlation of parcels with CC rules

Through the parcel button the user is able to choose the parcels to which each rule applies.

Select parcels relevant to the question: Do you have at least 0.01ha of the farm in the water protection zone?

Parcel name	Parcel ID	Mark relevant box
DA LI OVO RADJ DDDD	279	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
test	1244	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
aa	aa	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
test2	2222	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
test	test	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>

Figure 11: Selecting Parcels

Since the farm-related data is entered into the system, a list of all relevant rules is displayed to the end users, in order to simplify the visualization and group the complex regulations that the user need to be compliant. In each rule there are specific instructions explaining to the end users what they have to do in order to comply; and through a checklist the users can mark the completed instructions. Based on their answers, the rule is marked as complete or not (colour code) so the user can visually identify in a simple

and fast way what they still have to do in order to comply. Furthermore, through a drop down list, the users are able to view the specific rules that apply to their declared parcels separately. Finally, the users can attach relevant documents to each of the rules, if needed.

Figure 12: Cross Compliance list

During the inspection process, the users might be requested to open their information (documents, input/output and work dairy records) to the inspector. By clicking on the button “Make me visible” (green marked circle at the Figure 12) at the CC rules page, the users choose to make themselves visible to the inspectors and supply them access to their information. User data is maintained securely on the RECAP servers and always remains private to their owners, unless granted to be shared with the inspectors.

By selecting the “I” option at the top right of the CC rules page (red marked circle at the Figure 12) the users can view the inspection results grouped per CC rule along with any supportive documents that the inspectors have uploaded.

Line	Task	Must	Condition	Document	Start date	Deadline	CCRule	Inspector compliance	Self compliance
1	Cultivation is not allowed within a buffer strip of at least one meter from the banks of water courses.	No	There is no maximum width of the buffer strips (m)				GAEC 1	✗	✗
2	None	Yes		Farm input/ output records Farm work diary			GAEC 1	✗	✗
3	If the land slope is greater than 8% then the buffer strip should be 6 meters.	Yes	All surface water courses buffer strips apply				GAEC 1	✗	✗
4	Use of nitrous fertilizers is not allowed within a buffer strip of 2 meters from water courses.	No					GAEC 1	✗	✗
5	Farmers who irrigate within the holding should comply with authorization procedures deriving from the national legislation 3199/2003 for the irrigation water	Yes		License of water use			GAEC 2	✗	✗
6	Farmers who are members of Collective Irrigation Organizations should have the respective document from the Organization.	Yes					GAEC 2	✗	✗
7	None	Yes					GAEC 2	✗	✗
8	None	Yes		Farm input/ output records Farm work diary			GAEC 3	✗	✗
9	The farmer should maintain any kind of agricultural facilities in good condition, in order to prevent leakage of contaminants to the environment.	Yes					GAEC 3	✗	✗
10	The farmer should not dispose of any dangerous substances listed in the Annex of Directive 80/68/EEC, as adopted with the National Law 26857/553/1988 (B 196) onto the ground and into the groundwater	No					GAEC 3	✗	✗

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Figure 13: Cross Compliance rules details

In order to have an overview of their “obligations”, the users can click on the Self-Assessment button at the top left of the CC rules page and retrieve a total summary of what they should do and which documents are still missing.

Moreover, the farmer can check if the declared sub parcels added via the spatial component are compliant with the greening rules through the Greening calculator at the top left of the CC rules page.

In order to assist users, either farmers or inspectors, during an imminent inspection, the RECAP platform offers to the farmers the option to maintain input/ output and work dairies records. This functionality helps farmers to retrieve notes and details from the practices that can be useful in case of an inspection.

A. INPUT: BUING AGRICULTURAL SUPPLIES - SUPPLIERS DATA										
Line	Document number	Suppliers name	Suppliers address	Trade name	Ratio N-P-K (for fertilizers)	Number of packages	Total quantity (kg/lt)	Date of purchase	Type of product	Organic (N/O)
Add										

B. INPUT: FEED AND THEIR ADDITIVES - SUPPLIERS DATA												
Line	Document number	Suppliers name	Suppliers address	Number of packages	Total quantity (kg/lt)	Type of animal, age & productivity	Type of product	Date of purchase	Time period of operation	Organic (N/O)	GMO (N/O)	Medicated (N/O)
Add												

C. WORK DIARY										
Line	Document number	Parcel Serial No	Total area (ha)	Cultivation	Work	Trade name/variety	Quantity (kg/lt)	Type of product used	Date	Description of reason/remarks
Add										

D. OUTPUT: PRODUCED PRODUCTS - BUYERS DATA									
Line	Document number	Buyers name	Buyers address	Trade name/variety	Quantity	Date of purchase	Type of product		
Add									

Figure 14: Farmer's input log

Moreover, through the platform, the Paying Agencies (PAs)/ inspectors and farmers can communicate directly and the farmers can ask them specific questions and the PAs can reply. In like manner, inspectors can reach out to the farmer to request specific information before the inspection.

Reminders are also one of the most important functionality of the RECAP platform and can be categorized in three different types:

- Reminders based on calendar key dates that the users must remember.
- Notifications/alerts based on the results from the remote sensing process. In case a non-compliance is detected for a specific rule, users are alerted and they gain visibility and access to the same information that inspectors have.
- Users can create their own custom reminders that will be displayed either as a calendar, or as a notification along with the calendar key dates reminders.

SEPTEMBER, 2017						
Sun	Mon	Tue	Wed	Thu	Fri	Sat
27	28	29	30	1	2	
3	4	5	6	7	8	9
10	11	12	13	14	15	16
17	18	19	20	21	22	23
24	25	26	27	28	29	30

Figure 15: Reminders – View as a Calendar

Reminders (3 added)				
Line	Author	Description	Date of the event	Date to be reminded
1	239	Fertilization	2017-09-02	2017-08-31
2	239	Irrigation	2017-08-31	2017-08-29
3	239	Farmer reminder one!	2017-09-03	2017-09-01

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Figure 16: Reminders – View as a List

Other than farmers, consultants and farm staff will be able to have access to the RECAP platform and get the information of the farmers. Once the farmers grant access to their accounts, by defining role and access level, the consultant or the farm staff will be able to view farmer’s system. The consultants will have a view of all their clients’ fields and will be able to select a specific farmer to view their fields and check if there are any new reminders.

The Spatial component enables farmers to insert their fields to the system, by drawing the shape over the map. This shape is also editable if a mistake has happened.

Figure 17: Adding parcel geometry

Moreover, the farmers have access to maps containing information about:

- Time-series of Sentinel-2 background optical imagery for viewing only
- Habitat
- Natura sites
- Nitrate Vulnerable Zones
- Botanical Heritage Sites
- Watercourse maps
- Slope map (or DEM)
- Administrative boundaries and settlements
- Land Use/ Land Cover Maps, as detailed as possible
- ILOT and sub-ILOT
- LPIS (WMS or shp)
- Remote sensing alerts

The Remote sensing results are available to the farmers through the Spatial component interface.

3.1.2 Inspectors

The inspectors are defined by the PAs and they are able to view all the relevant checklists and maps for the farmer that they inspect in order to get ready for the inspection and help them decide if the inspected farmer is compliant with the regulations or not.

The inspectors can view a list of the farmers that they have to inspect in the Inspections menu and select a farmer to open the inspection form.

#	Kod Par	Year of Application	First Name	Last Name	Email Address	
1	1111111111	2016	Alex	ANTONIS	farmer_gr1@example.com	<input type="button" value="Open inspection Forms"/>
2	4444444444	2017	Nikos	NIKOLAOU	farmer_gr3@example.com	<input type="button" value="Open inspection Forms"/>
3	3333333333	2017	Dimitris	DIMITRIOU	farmer_gr2@example.com	<input type="button" value="Open inspection Forms"/>
4	2222222222	2017	Alex	ANTONIS	farmer_gr1@example.com	<input type="button" value="Close inspection Forms"/>

1 of 1

Figure 18: Inspections

Based on the farmer’s BPS application, the respective checklists are displayed to the inspector. In addition, some of the checklist fields get prepopulated based on the information provided by the farmer, saving valuable time for the inspector and minimizing the possibility of entering wrong information.

The screenshot shows a user interface for an inspection checklist. At the top, there are four tabs: "Final decision", "Schedule Inspection", "CCRules Checklist", and "Log History". Below the tabs is a progress bar consisting of 26 steps, labeled "Step 1" through "Step 26". Step 1 is currently active, indicated by a green circle and a line. Below the progress bar is a form titled "Checklist A1". The form contains several input fields with labels and placeholder text:

- Local office opekepe:
- Serial number of basic payment declaration:
- Perfecture:
- Perfecture code:
- Local public office of agriculture services:
- Agriculture code:
- Date of control from:
- Date of control to:

Figure 19: Inspection checklist

After the farmer’s permission to give access to their information, inspectors can view which rules apply to the farmer and gain visibility to the farmer’s documents, work diary and input/ outputs tables.

Figure 20: CC Rules checklists

Once the inspector fills in all the checklists with the relevant information, they can go to the “Final Decision” page. There they can define for each rule whether it is being followed by the farmer or not. When this task is finished, they can submit the final decision to the RECAP platform and a reporting email will be sent to the farmer and the PA.

Results

CC Rules	Select status from the list	Review
GAEC 1 : Establishment of buffer strips along watercourses	PENDING	0
GAEC 2 : Water abstraction	BREACH DETECTED	1
GAEC 3 : Groundwater	BREACH DETECTED	0
GAEC 6 : Maintaining the level of organic matter in soil	PENDING	0
GAEC 7a : Boundaries	PENDING	0
SMR 4 : Food and feed law	PENDING	4
SMR 5 : Restrictions on the use of substances having hormonal or thyrostatic action and beta-agonists in farm animals	PENDING	0
SMR 7 : Cattle identification and registration	PENDING	0
SMR 8 : Sheep and goat identification	PENDING	1
SMR 9 : Prevention and control of transmissible spongiform encephalopathies (TSEs)	PENDING	0
SMR 10 : Plant Protection Products (PPPs)	PENDING	4
SMR 11 : Welfare of calves	PENDING	0
SMR 12 : Welfare of pigs	PENDING	0
SMR 13 : Animal welfare	PENDING	0
None : None	PENDING	0

[Submit Final Decision](#)

Figure 21: Final Decision

Furthermore, Scheduler allows inspectors to create and visualize inspection events. Inspectors can schedule an inspection and the farmer receives an email that contains the date that they will be notified about the coming inspection. A notification is also displayed within the farmer’s app. Moreover, if the farmer has allowed access to his information, the inspector can view their scheduled events.

Figure 22: Scheduler

3.1.3 Paying Agencies

The PAs can select from a list an inspector and assign to them farmers that should be inspected. The selected inspectors have access to the farmers' BPS.

Figure 23: Inspectors management

The assigned inspectors are included in a list in the Inspectors menu and the PAs can view the details of the inspections process.

#	First Name	Last Name	Email Address	
1			inspector_gr@example.com	Manage Inspections
2	Kostas	KONSTANTINOU	inspector_gr1@example.com	Manage Inspections
3	Manolis	MANIKAS	inspector_gr2@example.com	Manage Inspections

1 of 1

Figure 24: Assigned inspectors list

Furthermore, the PA officers can retrieve valuable information from the extractor component that can help them to perform more targeted inspections and get insights on whether the farmers' responded correctly to the CC rules.

Another basic functionality of the 1st version of the RECAP platform that will be used by the PAs is the Remote Sensing products, including image classification derivatives, risk estimation products and vegetation indices, as well as RGB satellite images, using a set of Sentinel-2 images. The information that is returned by the Remote Sensing component for each farmer's declared parcel, is combined with auxiliary data and used within the RECAP platform to provide indications about specific CC rules.

In addition, the Spatial component provides PA officers and inspectors access to the spatial information generated by the Remote Sensing component and external spatial data. With the use of maps the users are able to visualize information needed for the selection and inspection process.

The results from the Remote sensing component are also displayed in the form of map controls in the user interface. Moreover, the PAs are able to select a bounding box on the map from the area that they are interested in, which triggers the remote sensing processes and returns the results of the Remote sensing analysis.

Figure 25: Remote sensing component view

The inspectors have access to this information before and during an inspection so that they can prove to a farmer on breaches detected by Remote sensing and also identify non-compliance when on-the-spot.

The following table summarises the main features of the web application per user.

Table 3: Main features of the web application per user

Farmers	Consultants	PAs	Inspectors
Farm management	Farm management	Inspector assignment	Inspections management
Cross Compliance checklist	Cross Compliance checklist	Inspections management	Inspection scheduler
Greening Calculator	Greening Calculator	Communication between farmers and PAs	Farmer's data management
Farmer's log/ Farmer's Inspection	Farmer's log/ Farmer's Inspection	Document repository	Document repository
Communication between farmers and PAs/ Inspectors	Communication between farmers and PAs/ Inspectors	Spatial component	Communication between farmers and Inspectors
Notifications/ Reminders	Notifications/ Reminders	Remote Sensing component	Spatial component
User roles	User roles	Business intelligence analysis tool (Extractor component)	
Spatial component	Spatial component		
Report problem	SDK component		

3.2 Mobile Application

3.2.1 Farmers

Using the mobile application, the farmers are able to view the CC Rules – Checklist (Figure 26) based on the data they have entered through the web application and they are also able to communicate with the PA in case of exceptional circumstances (Figure 27).

Figure 26: CC Rules - Checklist

Figure 27: Report a problem

Furthermore, the farmers are able to collect and store timestamped and geotagged photos from their fields on the My Documents menu. Specifically, the farmer is able to take photos from within the mobile application and they can view/ upload/ delete/edit all the documents and/ or images uploaded to RECAP and apply filters based on type/ tags/ CC rules, etc.

Figure 28: My Documents

3.2.2 Inspectors

The Inspectors are able to access the data related to the farm to be inspected either from the web application or from the mobile app. This is due to the necessity of having access to any data needed for OTSC.

The inspectors are able to fill in the inspection forms and view the CC Rules – checklists (Figure 29) during the inspection process through their mobile phones and can also take photos from within the app and upload them to the RECAP database (Figure 30) when connected to internet.

Figure 29: CC Rules - Checklist

Figure 30: My Documents

Moreover, the inspectors are able to capture new boundaries of the LPIS parcels, select spatial data layers and download this information for the selected farm parcels in order to prepare for the OTSC inspection.

Figure 31: Spatial component

The following table describes the main features of the mobile application per user role:

Table 4: Main features of the mobile application per user

Farmers	Inspectors
Cross Compliance Checklist	Inspections management
Upload timestamped/geotagged photos	Inspection scheduler
Communication between farmers and PAs/Inspectors	Communication between farmers and Inspectors
Notifications/ Reminders	Upload timestamped/geotagged photos
User roles	Document repository
Spatial component	Spatial component

4 Conclusions

This document describes the progress made in the WP3 providing information about the development and delivering the 1st version of the RECAP platform and its components. Additionally, this deliverable provides information about the RECAP platform functionality along with details on the changes compared the previous deliverables that described the architecture, the implementation approach and the technologies that were used for the development of the RECAP platform, the extraction and modeling tools and the software components developed.

There has been good progress in developing and integrating the components of the RECAP platform. However, there are still some key developments that are scheduled. The RECAP platform will be continuously improved from both feature and performance perspective and quality of the provided information. This first release of the RECAP platform represents a solid and functional version that will gradually, with further development, result to a valuable tool for all users over the next period. Moreover, the current version of the platform is expected to be further developed and customized to the users' specific needs, which it will go through the co-production and pilot phases. These adjustments will be presented in the final deliverable D3.5 "Final version of revised product backlog and development report".

5 References

- D2.2 Report of user requirements in relation to the RECAP platform
(Confidential deliverable not available on the web)
- D3.1 RECAP System Architecture
https://www.recap-h2020.eu/wp-content/uploads/2017/03/d.3.1_system_architecture.pdf
- D3.3 Software components development
https://www.recap-h2020.eu/wp-content/uploads/2017/09/d.3.3_Software_components_development.pdf

6 Annexes

6.1 Annex I – RECAP Testing Scenarios

The complete list of the testing scenarios which were created for RECAP is presented in this appendix. Those tests were followed upon new feature deployment (during development) and some were executed manually by humans and some automatically written in code. The information provided for each are:

Test Steps: The steps needed to follow this test

Expected results: Where should the platform or the mobile navigation take the user upon successful completion

Actual results: The results of the latest run test

Fail Cases: The scenarios which trigger validations or the test mission to fail

Testing Date: When was, the test followed the last time

Completion: If the test was successful the last time

Automated: If the test is manual or automated (automated tests do not usually execute manually)

6.1.1 Login Web

Test Steps:

- Navigate to <http://app.recap-h2020.eu/>
- Fill email
- Fill password
- Click Log in button

Expected results:

Dashboard Page

Actual results:

Dashboard Page

Fail Cases:

- Leave email blank (error message explaining why login failed)
- Leave password blank (error message explaining why login failed)

Completion: Done

Automated: Yes

6.1.2 Registration Web

Test Steps:

- Navigate to <http://app.recap-h2020.eu/>
- Fill email
- Fill password
- Fill repeat password
- Click submit button

Expected results:

SignUp Page

Confirmation email

Actual results:

SignUp Page
Confirmation email

Fail Cases:

- Leave email blank (Enter a valid email address)
- Use already existing email (error message explaining why registration failed)
- Leave password blank (validation error)
- No repeat password (validation error)

Completion: Done

Automated: Yes

6.1.3 Farm Profile Page Step BPS

Test Steps:

- Navigate to <http://app.recap-h2020.eu/dashboard>
- Navigate to <http://app.recap-h2020.eu/farm-profile/steps/bps>
- Click Farm Profile
- Fill gaps and tick boxes
- Go to next page

Expected results:

Fill gaps, tick boxes and go to next page

Actual results:

Fill gaps, tick boxes and go to next page

Completion: Done

Automated: Yes

6.1.4 Farm Profile Page Step 1

Test Steps:

- Navigate to <http://app.recap-h2020.eu/dashboard>
- Click on Farm Profile and next button
- Navigate to <http://app.recap-h2020.eu/farm-profile/steps/01>
- Click on edit button
- Fill gaps and tick boxes
- Click on save button
- Go to next page

Expected results:

Work right all test steps

Actual results:

Work right all test steps

Completion: Done

Automated: Yes

6.1.5 Farm Profile Page Step 2

Test Steps:

- Navigate to <http://app.recap-h2020.eu/dashboard>

- Click on Farm Profile and next buttons
- Navigate to <http://app.recap-h2020.eu/farm-profile/steps/02>
- Click on tick button
- Go to next page

Expected results:

Work right all test steps

Actual results:

Work right all test steps

Completion: Done

Automated: Yes

This step is repeated till step 16

6.1.6 Farm Profile Page Step Questionnaire

Test Steps:

- Navigate to <http://app.recap-h2020.eu/dashboard>
- Click on Farm Profile and next buttons
- Navigate to <http://app.recap-h2020.eu/farm-profile/steps/17>
- Click on tick buttons
- Click in parcels button
- Click on tick buttons
- Click on save button
- Click on finish button

Expected results:

Work right all test steps

Actual results:

Work right all test steps

Completion: Done

Automated: Yes

6.1.7 CC Rules-Checklist Comments

Test Steps:

- Navigate to <http://app.recap-h2020.eu/dashboard>
- Click on CC Rules-Checklist button
- Navigate to <http://app.recap-h2020.eu/ccrules>
- Click on a yellow box
- Click on comments button
- Navigate to <http://app.recap-h2020.eu/ccrule-single/CC%20Rule%20-GAEC%201>
- Add comment
- Post the comment

Expected results:

Post a comment

Actual results:

Post a comment

Completion: Done

Automated: Yes

6.1.8 Log History

Test Steps:

- Navigate to <http://app.recap-h2020.eu/dashboard>
- Click on image button
- Click on log history button
- Navigate to <http://app.recap-h2020.eu/log-history>
- Click on arrow button

Expected results:

Navigate log history pages

Actual results:

Navigate log history pages

Completion: Done

Automated: Yes

6.1.9 Maps

Test Steps:

- Navigate to <http://app.recap-h2020.eu/dashboard>
- Click on Maps button
- Navigate to <http://app.recap-h2020.eu/maps>
- Click on search write a parcel id and click enter
- Click on a parcel's id button

Expected results:

Navigate maps page and test all the option

Actual results:

Navigate maps page and test all the option

Completion: Done

Automated: Yes

6.1.10 Reminders

Test Steps:

- Navigate to <http://app.recap-h2020.eu/dashboard>
- Click on Reminders button
- Navigate to <http://app.recap-h2020.eu/reminders>
- Click on add button
- Fill gaps and tick boxes
- Create a new reminder

Expected results:

Create a new reminder

Actual results:

Create a new reminder

Completion: Done

Automated: Yes

6.1.11 Roles

Test Steps:

- Navigate to <http://app.recap-h2020.eu/dashboard>
- Click on Roles button
- Navigate to <http://app.recap-h2020.eu/roles>
- Click on add button
- Fill gaps and tick boxes
- Create a new role account

Expected results:

Create a new role account

Actual results:

Create a new role account

Completion: Done

Automated: Yes

6.1.12 Work Diary- A. INPUT: BUING AGRICULTAR SUPPLIES – SUPPLIERS DATA

Test Steps:

- Navigate to <http://app.recap-h2020.eu/dashboard>
- Click on Work Diary button
- Navigate to <http://app.recap-h2020.eu/work-diary>
- Click on A. INPUT: BUING AGRICULTAR SUPPLIES – SUPPLIERS DATA
- Click on add button
- Click to save the new row

Expected results:

Add a new row

Actual results:

Add a new row

Fail Cases:

Completion: Done

Automated: Yes

6.1.13 Work Diary- B. INPUT: BUING AGRICULTAR SUPPLIES – SUPPLIERS DATA

Test Steps:

- Navigate to <http://app.recap-h2020.eu/dashboard>
- Click on Work Diary button
- Navigate to <http://app.recap-h2020.eu/work-diary>

- Click on B. INPUT: FEED AND THEIR ADDITIVES – SUPPLIERS DATA
- Click on add button
- Click to save the new row

Expected results:

Add a new row

Actual results:

Add a new row

Fail Cases:

Completion: Done

Automated: Yes

6.1.14 Work Diary- C. WORK DIARY

Test Steps:

- Navigate to <http://app.recap-h2020.eu/dashboard>
- Click on Work Diary button
- Navigate to <http://app.recap-h2020.eu/work-diary>
- Click on C. WORK DIARY
- Click on add button
- Click to save the new row

Expected results:

Add a new row

Actual results:

Add a new row

Fail Cases:

Completion: Done

Automated: Yes

6.1.15 Work Diary- D. OUTPUT: PRODUCED PRODUCTS – BUYERS DATA

Test Steps:

- Navigate to <http://app.recap-h2020.eu/dashboard>
- Click on Work Diary button
- Navigate to <http://app.recap-h2020.eu/work-diary>
- Click on D. OUTPUT: PRODUCED PRODUCTS – BUYERS DATA
- Click on add button
- Click to save the new row

Expected results:

Add a new row

Actual results:

Add a new row

Fail Cases:

Completion: Done

Automated: Yes

6.1.16 Validation: Work Diary- A. INPUT: BUING AGRICULTAR SUPPLIES – SUPPLIERS DATA

Test Steps:

- Navigate to <http://app.recap-h2020.eu/dashboard>
- Click on Work Diary button
- Navigate to <http://app.recap-h2020.eu/work-diary>
- Click on A. INPUT: BUING AGRICULTAR SUPPLIES – SUPPLIERS DATA
- Click on add button
- Click to save the new row

Expected results:

Displaying validation error warnings

Actual results:

Displaying validation error warnings

Fail Cases:

Completion: Done

Automated: Yes

6.1.17 Validation: Work Diary- B. INPUT: BUING AGRICULTAR SUPPLIES – SUPPLIERS DATA

Test Steps:

- Navigate to <http://app.recap-h2020.eu/dashboard>
- Click on Work Diary button
- Navigate to <http://app.recap-h2020.eu/work-diary>
- Click on B. INPUT: FEED AND THEIR ADDITIVES – SUPPLIERS DATA
- Click on add button
- Click to save the new row

Expected results:

Displaying validation error warnings

Actual results:

Displaying validation error warnings

Fail Cases:

Completion: Done

Automated: Yes

6.1.18 Validation: Work Diary- C. WORK DIARY

Test Steps:

- Navigate to <http://app.recap-h2020.eu/dashboard>
- Click on Work Diary button
- Navigate to <http://app.recap-h2020.eu/work-diary>
- Click on C. WORK DIARY
- Click on add button
- Click to save the new row

Expected results:

Displaying validation error warnings

Actual results:

Displaying validation error warnings

Fail Cases:

Completion: Done

Automated: Yes

6.1.19 Validation: Work Diary- D. OUTPUT: PRODUCED PRODUCTS – BUYERS DATA

Test Steps:

- Navigate to <http://app.recap-h2020.eu/dashboard>
- Click on Work Diary button
- Navigate to <http://app.recap-h2020.eu/work-diary>
- Click on D. OUTPUT: PRODUCED PRODUCTS – BUYERS DATA
- Click on add button
- Click to save the new row

Expected results:

Displaying validation error warnings

Actual results:

Displaying validation error warnings

Completion: Done

Automated: Yes

6.1.20 Validation: Farm Profile Page Step BPS

Test Steps:

- Navigate to <http://app.recap-h2020.eu/dashboard>
- Navigate to <http://app.recap-h2020.eu/farm-profile/steps/bps>
- Click Farm Profile
- Click next button

Expected results:

Displaying validation error warnings

Actual results:

Displaying validation error warnings

Completion: Done

Automated: Yes

6.1.21 Validation: Farm Profile Page Step 1

Test Steps:

- Navigate to <http://app.recap-h2020.eu/dashboard>
- Click on Farm Profile and next button
- Navigate to <http://app.recap-h2020.eu/farm-profile/steps/01>
- Click on edit button

- Click on save button

Expected results:

Displaying validation error warnings

Actual results:

Displaying validation error warnings

Completion: Done

Automated: Yes

6.1.22 Validation: Farm Profile Page Step 3

Test Steps:

- Navigate to <http://app.recap-h2020.eu/dashboard>
- Click on Farm Profile and next buttons
- Navigate to <http://app.recap-h2020.eu/farm-profile/steps/03>
- Click on edit button
- Click on save button

Expected results:

Displaying validation error warnings

Actual results:

Displaying validation error warnings

Completion: Done

Automated: Yes

6.1.23 Validation: Farm Profile Page Step 14

Test Steps:

- Navigate to <http://app.recap-h2020.eu/dashboard>
- Click on Farm Profile and next buttons
- Navigate to <http://app.recap-h2020.eu/farm-profile/steps/14>
- Click on edit button
- Click on save button

Expected results:

Displaying validation error warnings

Actual results:

Displaying validation error warnings

Completion: Done

Automated: Yes

6.1.24 Validation: Reminders

Test Steps:

- Navigate to <http://app.recap-h2020.eu/dashboard>
- Click on Reminders button
- Navigate to <http://app.recap-h2020.eu/reminders>
- Click on add button
- Click save button

Expected results:

Displaying validation error warnings

Actual results:

Displaying validation error warnings

Completion: Done

Automated: Yes

6.1.25 Validation: Roles

Test Steps:

- Navigate to <http://app.recap-h2020.eu/dashboard>
- Click on Roles button
- Navigate to <http://app.recap-h2020.eu/roles>
- Click on add button
- Click on save button

Expected results:

Displaying validation error warnings

Actual results:

Displaying validation error warnings

Completion: Done

Automated: Yes

6.1.26 Add Geometry

Test Steps:

- Navigate to <http://app.recap-h2020.eu/dashboard>
- Click on Farm Profile button
- Click next button
- Navigate to <http://app.recap-h2020.eu/farm-profile/steps/01>
- Click on add geometry button
- Click on delete geometry button

Expected results:

Add geometry and then delete the geometry

Actual results:

Add geometry

Fail Cases:

Cannot delete the geometry

Completion: Done

Automated: Yes